

Study of binary systems and determination of latent transition temperatures (LTTs) of nonmesogenic components

N. G. Makwana^{a*} and A. V. Doshi^b

^aChemistry Department, Smt. D. J. Shah Parivar Science College, Dholka-387 810, Gujarat, India

E-mail : ngmakwana@yahoo.com

^bChemistry Department, Matushri Virbhaima Mahila Science and Home Science College, Rajkot-360 007, Gujarat, India

Manuscript received 11 October 2006, revised 23 November 2007, accepted 26 November 2007

Abstract : The latent ability to exhibit mesophase transition temperatures of a substance is determined for non-mesomorphic components of the binary systems, viz. Schiff's bases (B₁, B₂, B₃) by mixing them with a monotropic nematic component (A) as a common component. Components of the binary systems were prepared by established methods of preparation. The transition temperature of pure components and binary mixtures were observed through hot stage polarizing microscope. The phase diagrams are drawn for transition temperatures versus mole% of component (A). Analytical data support the structure of the molecules.

The latent transition temperature of each non liquid crystal component is determined by the extrapolation of nematic-isotropic (or vice versa) transition curve to zero mole% of (A). The values of latent transition temperatures (LTTs) for different Schiff's bases are determined and well agree with previously work. Thus, reliability of extrapolation method is raised and credibility to the conclusions already drawn earlier is supported by present investigation.

Keywords : Nematic, smectic, mesogen, mesomorphism.

Introduction

Presently, the independent existence of a liquid crystalline state like solid, liquid and gas is fully accepted. Therefore, same nonliquid crystalline substances though geometrically resemble to the structure like liquid crystalline substance should have the potential to exhibit liquid crystalline state at a certain temperature below their melting point. Substances in their binary mixtures with a liquid crystalline substance or even with a nonliquid crystal substance can give rise to "mixed liquid crystal" formation over a range of temperature and composition. The range of composition over which liquid crystallinity is observed depends upon the degree of similarity of the molecules of the nonliquid crystal and liquid crystal substances in shape, size, polarity of the end groups and polarizability.

It has been possible to predict a temperature known as the "latent transition temperature" (LTT) for nonliquid crystalline components with a latent ability to exhibit mesomorphism on the basis of extrapolation of the mesomorphic-isotropic (or vice versa) transition curve. One has to search to establish experimental condition to detect liquid crystalline phase, for which determination of LTT is an important.

Several binary systems have been studied by number of researchers consisting of one, none or both components as mesomorphs, with an induction of smectic or/and nematic mesophase by mixing two components¹⁻¹⁰.

Six binary systems have been studied presently with 4-(4'-*n*-alkoxy benzoyloxy)-3-chloro phenylazo benzenes [propyloxy (A₁) and butyloxy (A₂)] as common components (A).

para substituted Schiff's bases (B : B₁ : B₂ B₆).

X-C₆H₄-CH=N-C₆H₄-Y (where, X = -OCH₃, -Cl and Y = -CH₃, -Cl, -OCH₃) as component (B).

Experimental

Preparation of components :

Component (A) of binary systems was prepared by condensing 4-*n*-alkoxy benzoyl chloride (propyloxy and butyloxy) with 4-hydroxy-3-chloro phenyl azo benzene by usual established method (m.p. 86 °C)^{11,12}. The resulting products were purified by silica gel column chromatography using petroleum ether (60–80 °C) and ethyl acetate mixture (95 : 5) as eluent and crystallized by alcohol. Schiff's bases (B) were prepared by established

*Address for communication : H/8, Ganga Apartment, Opp. G. D. High School, Saijpurbhoga, Naroda Road, Ahmedabad-382 345, Gujarat, India.

Fig. 1. Phase diagrams of binary systems.

method⁴. Melting point and other physical data of Schiff's bases well compares with the reported values⁴⁻⁸. Binary mixtures were prepared by routine method⁴. The transition temperatures of the binary mixtures were observed through hot stage polarizing microscope.

Results and discussion

The transition temperatures of pure components and binary mixtures as well as mole% and temperatures of eutectic point are derived from phase diagrams and

recorded in Tables 1(a) and (b). The composition and temperature range over which the liquid crystal mesophase is observed depends upon the degree of similarity of the molecules of the components A and B of a binary system in shape, size, polarity of terminal groups and polarizability. The constituent components of all the binary systems are elongated lath-like and structurally similar except -Cl group attached with central phenyl ring at the lateral position. Hence, the intermolecular forces of attraction are capable enough to maintain parallel

Table 1(a)

Sl. no.	Component-B X-C ₆ H ₄ -CH=N-C ₆ H ₄ -Y		Type of mesophase	Mole% of component-A ₁											Eutectic point	
	X	Y		0	10	20	30	40	50	60	70	80	90	100	Temp. (°C)	Mole (%)
1.	-OCH ₃	-CH ₃	Smectic	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
			Nematic	-	-	(58.0)	(62.0)	(62.5)	(59.0)	(56.5)	(68.5)	(76.0)	(80.5)	(81.0)	-	-
			Isotropic	92.0	89.0	84.0	76.0	81.5	86.0	89.5	92.0	95.0	98.0	101.0	75.5	29.5
2.	-OCH ₃	-Cl	Smectic	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
			Nematic	-	-	-	(61.0)	(65.5)	(70.0)	(73.0)	(76.0)	(78.5)	(80.0)	(81.0)	-	-
			Isotropic	93.0	88.5	82.0	74.0	72.0	79.0	85.5	91.0	95.5	99.0	101.0	69.0	35.5
3.	-Cl	-OCH ₃	Smectic	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
			Nematic	-	-	-	-	-	(70.0)	(66.0)	(70.0)	(73.5)	(77.0)	(81.0)	-	-
			Isotropic	123.5	120.0	115.0	108.0	101.0	92.5	88.0	92.0	95.0	97.0	101.0	88.0	59.0

Value in parenthesis indicate monotropy.

Table 1(b)

Sl. no.	Component-B X-C ₆ H ₄ -CH=N-C ₆ H ₄ -Y		Type of mesophase	Mole% of component-A ₂											Eutectic point	
	X	Y		0	10	20	30	40	50	60	70	80	90	100	Temp. (°C)	Mole (%)
1.	-OCH ₃	-CH ₃	Smectic	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
			Nematic	-	-	(51.0)	(55.0)	(60.5)	(70.0)	(79.5)	(87.0)	(93.0)	(97.0)	(100.0)	-	-
			Isotropic	92.0	87.5	81.0	72.0	83.0	92.0	99.0	103.0	106.5	108.0	110.0	72.0	30.0
2.	-OCH ₃	-Cl	Smectic	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		
			Nematic	-	-	(70.0)	(73.0)	(71.5)	(69.5)	(78.0)	(85.0)	(91.5)	(96.0)	(100.0)	-	-
			Isotropic	93.0	88.5	83.0	78.0	80.0	89.0	93.0	96.0	100.5	106.5	110.0	75.0	37.5
3.	-Cl	-OCH ₃	Smectic	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		
			Nematic	-	-	-	(84.0)	(81.5)	(77.0)	(71.0)	(81.0)	(89.0)	(95.5)	(100.0)	-	-
			Isotropic	123.5	120.0	115.0	109.0	101.0	91.0	90.0	98.0	104.0	108.0	110.0	85.5	55.0

Value in parenthesis indicate monotropy.

orientation of molecule even in the floating condition within definite range of temperature and composition in a mixed melt. Thus nematogenic liquid crystalline mesophase is exhibited by some binary mixtures of a system. The minimum proportion of composition required to disrupt completely the mesomorphic parallel molecular alignments of component (A₁) in a mixed melt are 80.0, 79.0 and 52.0 mole% of components (B₁, B₂ and B₃) respectively, for nematic mesophase. Thus the disruption caused by nonmesogenic components (B) is in the expected⁴ order of the polarity of terminal groups. Though -CH₃ and -Cl terminals are equally compatible,

The minimum proportion of composition required to disrupt completely the mesomorphic parallel molecular alignments of component (A₂) in a mixed melt are 81.0, 87.0 and 71.0 mole% of component B₄, B₅ and B₆ respectively, for nematic mesophase. Thus the disruption

caused by nonmesogenic components (B) is in the expected⁴ order of the polarity of terminal groups. Though -CH₃ and -Cl terminals are equally compatible, however minimum proportion of components (B) required to disrupt mesomorphic alignments in a mixed melt are 81.0 and 87.0 mole% of component (B₄ and B₅). This is due to the negligible difference in melting points of Schiff's bases B₄ and B₅.

-OCH₃ terminal group is relatively more polar than -CH₃ and -Cl. On the other hand -CH₃ and -Cl are almost equivalent with each other in respect to polarity. Moreover all the three Schiff's bases under discussion invariably contain -OCH₃ as right or left terminal with -CH₃ or -Cl. Thus molecular polarity of Schiff's bases B₁, B₂, B₃ is almost equivalent. Therefore difference in phase diagram observed is varied with the variation of common components (A₁) and (A₂) as well as difference in the

Table 2

Sl. no.	Predicted latent transition temperature of Schiff's base (°C)						
	Present investigation		Previous work				
	With A ₁	With A ₂	Ref. 4	Ref. 5	Ref. 6	Ref. 7	Ref. 8
1.	42.0 (B1)	46.5 (B4)	40.0	39.0	39.0	39.0	40.0
2.	44.0 (B2)	43.0 (B5)	42.0	–	–	–	–
3.	74.0 (B3)	72.0 (B6)	73.0	–	–	–	–

melting points of constituent components of binary systems. But component A₁ and A₂ are propyl and butyl homologues of same series. Therefore difference in the shape of solid-isotropic transition curves of binary systems 1, 2, 4 and 5 are almost same and isotropic-nematic transition curves of binary systems 1, 3, 5 and 6 are more or less same. Thus difference in melting points of constituent components of binary systems causes variation in shape and monotropic transition temperature of curves of present binary systems. Monotropic nematic mesophase is persisted up to 80.0, 79.0, 52.0, 81.0, 87.0 and 71.0 mole% of components (B). These values are nearly equivalent i.e. differs by 8.0 to 16.0 mole% for all the binary system except third binary system in which observed difference is relatively little more. But it is observed from phase diagrams 1 to 6, that, transition curves are initially more or less straight following the law of mixtures ideally and monotropic crystalline property is persuade to such an extent which sets the smooth trend of bend in transition curves. Thus LTTs determined Schiff's bases are reliable and hence reliability of extrapolation method to determine LTT of nonmesomorphs is raised by present investigation.

The latent transition temperatures (LTTs) are determined from the phase diagram drawn for mole% of component (A) versus transition temperature in °C by extrapolation of nematic-isotropic or vice versa transition curve to zero mole% of A (Fig. 1). The values of LTTs are determined from present investigation are recorded in Table 2 and compared favourably with each other in present work and previous work⁴⁻⁸.

Components (A₁ and A₂) are monotropic nematic itself with its monotropic transition temperatures at 81.0 °C, 100.0 °C and melting temperatures at 101.0 °C, 110.0 °C respectively. From the phase diagrams of the binary system 1 to 6, it is observed that monotropic nematic mesophase appears within the definite range of composition and temperature because components (A₁ and A₂) are being monotropic nematic. Monotropic nematic components (A)

did not promote to smectic mesophase in the mixed melt. Adhering forces of attractions maintained parallel alignment of molecules in a mixed melt but intermolecular adhering forces of attraction fails to keep molecules in the layered arrangement i.e. no smectic mesophase is induced in any of the binary mixture of systems. Extrapolated values for B₁ to B₆ are 42.0, 44.0, 74.0, 46.5, 43.0 and 72.0 °C respectively. These are reliable values because monotropy persisted up to 80.0, 79.0, 52.0, 81.0, 87.0 and 71.0 mole % of respective components (B). Thus reliability of extrapolation method of determining LTTs of nonmesogenic component is well supported by present investigation.

Conclusions :

LTT determined for nonmesogenic components of binary systems well compared with each other and pervious work. Thus, credibility of extrapolation method is well supported by present investigation.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to present Head, Dr. C. N. Murthy and Ex-Head, Dr. N. D. Jadav for their valuable co-operation. Thanks are due to the Director, Central Salts and Marine Chemicals Research Institute, Bhavnagar for the analysis of samples.

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